

Corrosion inhibition of mild steel by pentyltriphenylphosphoniumbromide in acid medium – Part-II

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Abstract : The efficiency of pentyltriphenylphosphoniumbromide (PTPPB) as corrosion inhibitor for mild steel in H_2SO_4 ($10^{-3} M$, $10^{-5} M$, $10^{-7} M$) was investigated by electrochemical methods like study state galvanostatic and potentiostatic polarization measurements. The dissolution parameters such as corrosion current, passive current, flade potential, cathodic and anodic Tafel slopes and efficiencies were determined and studied at four different temperatures (298 K, 308 K, 318 K, 328 K). The optimum concentration of this compound for maximum inhibition efficiency was determined by galvanostatic method. PTPPB gave more than 93% inhibition in presence of $10^{-3} M H_2SO_4$ at 298 K. Potentiodynamic polarization studies revealed that PTPPB is mixed inhibitor and good passivator in 1 N H_2SO_4 . According to temperature kinetics PTPPB obeyed Temkin's and Freundlich adsorption isotherm, due to adsorption on metal surface. Certain quantum chemical parameters have been calculated to reinforce the electrochemical results.

Keywords : Corrosion, inhibition efficiency, mild steel, pentyltriphenylphosphoniumbromide.

Introduction

In the contemporary world metal has become integral part of life of human beings and therefore, the urgent need is to prevent it being corroded to its maximum extent if not stop completely. For that the urgent need is to investigate and detect inhibitor to determine the effect of inhibition and investigate the mode of inhibition. The objective of the present investigation has been to study the mechanism of adsorption of pentyltriphenylphosphoniumbromide (PTPPB) which act as corrosion inhibitor in acidic solution¹⁻⁷. This present study describe the role of pentyltriphenylphosphoniumbromide^{8,9} as an inhibitor during anodic dissolution of mild steel and cathodic reduction of oxygen.

The primary data have been collected on various aspects of corrosion of mild steel in sulphuric acid in the presence of PTPPB. The result is supplemented with temperature kinetics^{10,11}, infrared studies¹², scanning electron microscopy¹³ and quantum chemical studies^{14,15}.

Results and discussion

Galvanostatic studies in presence of pentyltriphenylphosphoniumbromide (PTPPB) :

In Table 1 the following information regarding inhibi-

Table 1. Corrosion parameters of mild steel in 1 N H_2SO_4 in the presence of PTPPB by galvanostatic studies

Temp. (K)	Conc. (mol^{-1})	$-E_{Corr}$ (mV)	b_c (mV/dec)	I_{Corr} (mA/cm^2)	I (%)
298	10^{-3}	440	185	0.28	93
	10^{-5}	483	115	1.3	70
	10^{-7}	482	125	2.0	56
	H_2SO_4	470	140	4.6	-
308	10^{-3}	514	245	0.6	88
	10^{-5}	470	100	1.5	70
	10^{-7}	476	95	1.7	66
	H_2SO_4	465	55	5.1	-
318	10^{-3}	512	225	1.6	82
	10^{-5}	492	115	5.3	41
	10^{-7}	489	80	5.6	37
	H_2SO_4	455	45	9.0	-
328	10^{-3}	510	105	3.8	68
	10^{-5}	456	60	6.0	50
	10^{-7}	500	55	9.0	25
	H_2SO_4	450	50	12.0	-

tor can be received by Tafel slopes. From the polarization data it can be seen that inhibitor act by both ways i.e.

(i) Blocking the active site during cathodic polariza-

tion the active site with Br⁻ providing active synergistic effect to this process of inhibition. PTPPB therefore, in acidic media undergoes small protonation reaction and form protonated species as per reaction given below.

(ii) During anodic polarization the metal dissolution the anodic current value increases the surface metal atom combined with hydroxide, Br⁻ ion and other ion present in the solution the adsorbed metal hydroxide (M-OH)_{ads} which form of adduct of the type (M-In)_{ads} or type (M-OH-In)_{ads}/(M-In-Br)_{ads}/(M-In-OH-Br)_{ads}/(M-In-Br-OH)_{ads}/(M-Br-OH-In)_{ads}.

Thermodynamic and adsorption studies on acid corrosion of mild steel in the presence of PTPPB :

In Table 2 the heat of adsorption *Q*, and effective activation energy *E*_{eff} have been calculated and it indicates that it is chemisorbed on the mild steel. Since the

Table 2. Calculated value of *Q* and *E*_{eff} for the corrosion of mild steel in 1 N H₂SO₄ in the presence of PTPPB

Concentration (mol L ⁻¹)	- <i>Q</i> (kcal mol ⁻¹)	<i>E</i> _{eff} (kcal mol ⁻¹)
10 ⁻³	18.4	23.00
10 ⁻⁵	23.0	21.62
10 ⁻⁷	0	20.70
H ₂ SO ₄	-	13.80

corrosion rates are directly related to corrosion current, the inhibitor efficiencies I% for different concentrations of PTPPB at 298 K, 308 K, 318 K and 328 K were calculated and tabulated in Table 3. The corrosion data has been analyzed from the value of surface coverage and adsorption isotherm.

Potentiostatic polarization studies : The effects of PTPPB from the graph, the anodic dissolution parameters (*i*_c, *E*_{pp}, *I*_p) of mild steel in 1 N sulfuric acid solution at various concentration of the PTPPB can be calculated and they are reported in Table 4. It has been concluded at the end that passivity is dependent on the concentration of the PTPPB and depends on the already adsorbed Br⁻ from the solution that assist the formation of the passive layer.

Infrared spectral studies :

Table 5 shows that on comparing the spectra of pure additive with that of adsorbed. It can be seen that many

Table 3. Corrosion parameters of mild steel in 1 N H₂SO₄ in the presence of PTPPB by thermodynamic studies

Temp. (K)	Conc. (mol L ⁻¹)	<i>i</i> _{corr} (mA/cm ²)	log <i>i</i> _{corr}	<i>I</i> (%)	θ	θ/1-θ
298	10 ⁻³	0.28	-0.5528	93	0.93	13.28
	10 ⁻⁵	1.30	0.11394	70	0.70	2.33
	10 ⁻⁷	2.00	0.3010	56	0.56	1.27
	H ₂ SO ₄	4.60	0.6627	-	-	-
308	10 ⁻³	0.6	-0.2218	88	0.88	7.33
	10 ⁻⁵	1.5	0.1760	70	0.70	2.33
	10 ⁻⁷	1.7	0.2304	66	0.66	1.50
	H ₂ SO ₄	5.1	0.70757	-	-	-
318	10 ⁻³	1.6	0.2041	82	0.82	4.55
	10 ⁻⁵	5.3	0.7242	41	0.41	0.69
	10 ⁻⁷	5.6	0.7481	37	0.37	1.70
	H ₂ SO ₄	9.0	0.9542	-	-	-
328	10 ⁻³	3.8	0.5797	68	0.68	2.12
	10 ⁻⁵	6.0	0.7781	50	0.50	1.00
	10 ⁻⁷	9.0	0.9542	25	0.25	0.33
	H ₂ SO ₄	12.0	1.0791	-	-	-

Table 4. Electrochemical parameters for anodic dissolution of mild steel in 1 N H₂SO₄ in the presence of PTPPB

Solutions	Conc.	<i>I</i> _c × 10 ² (mA cm ⁻²)	<i>I</i> _p (mA cm ⁻²)	<i>E</i> _{pp} (mV (Range))
H ₂ SO ₄	1 N	2.81	1.25	475-1550
PTPPB	10 ⁻³	-	-	-
	10 ⁻⁵	2.51	0.44	550-1500
	10 ⁻⁷	3.16	0.15	475-1495

Table 5. Infrared bands for pure and adsorbed (on silica gel) PTPPB

Inhibitor	(C-H) bend. Ar. sub (cm ⁻¹)	(P-Ar) str. (cm ⁻¹)	(P-CH ₂) str. (cm ⁻¹)	(C-C) Ar Str. (cm ⁻¹)
PTPPB	691.41	1484.03, 1159.69, 996	1436.90	1586.11
(PTPPB) _{ads}	691.48	-	1441	-

predominant peaks have either disappeared or shifted to higher frequencies or appear with reduced intensities. Now it has been confirmed that adsorption of these additive is taking place on silica gel. The purpose of IR adsorption studies here is to show that these additive are adsorbed to a certain extent on silica gel. It is anticipated that this adsorption shall also be taken place on mild steel surface as well. Because it has Fe as a major constituent and the vacant *d*-orbital of Fe will be expected to have some interaction with the de-localized electrons associated with this additive.

Scanning electron microscopy :

Scanning electron microscopy of mild steel surface exposed to 1 N sulfuric acid in the presence of 10^{-3} M and 10^{-7} M PTPPB concentrations respectively at magnification, from Fig. 1(c) and (d) shows almost 93% coverage of the metal surface by inhibitor molecule. The overall result gives an idea that the PTPPB is a very effective inhibitor at 298 K and supplement the earlier results obtained from galvanostatic and potentiostatic techniques.

is expected from quantum calculation and this may cause the cracks in protective covering layer. This is also the reason that it is a good passivator at lower concentration and not at higher concentration. But the higher value of synergistic effect of Br^- and less steric hindrance makes PTPPB a better inhibitor. From the HOMO and LUMO value it can be seen that additive could be an effective inhibitor because of synergetic effect of Br^- with the help of Table 6.

Fig. 1. SEM images of (A) mild steel, (B) mild steel in 1 N H_2SO_4 , (C) 10^{-3} M PTPPB and (D) 10^{-7} M PTPPB.

Quantum chemical analysis :

The relation between inhibition characteristics and quantum chemical data shows that $\log I_{\text{COR}}$ mostly depends upon the energy of the HOMO and LUMO. In addition to the data, it can also be related to dipole moment charge on phosphorous and the shapes of the additive. The energy of HOMO is the theoretical analogue of the ionization potential of the additive whereas, the energy of LUMO represent electron affinity of the substance, that is why good donor and bad acceptor will be indicator of good inhibitor. Dipole charge value indicate that there is a possibility of donation of electron in the metal surface. In case of PTPPB, as shown in Fig. 2(a) and (b), do not make them a perfect donor of electron as

Experimental

Preparation of PTPPB : All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. 1.0 ml of triphenylphosphine was dissolved in minimum quantity of toluene and 1.2 mol of pentyl bromide was added to it. The mixture was refluxed for 4–6 h the solid was filtered and washed with excess toluene. The white crystals of PTPPB were obtained. The solid was crystallized from CHCl_3 /petroleum ether, characterized by standard techniques and melting point was recorded 442 K. Mild steel grade IS-226 sample used for corrosion studies. The dimensions of specimen were 0.8 cm \times 0.8 cm \times 0.2 cm. Each mild steel specimen were coated with epoxy resin (araldite) and then

Fig. 2. Optimized geometry of PTPPB : (A) space filled model, (B) isosurface of total charge density, (C) ball and stick model and (D) electrostatic potential mapped onto 3-D isosurface of total charge density.

Table 6. Optimized AM1 parameters for PTPPB using Hyperchem

Sr. No.	Inhibitors	PTPPB
1.	No. of electrons	123
2.	Total energy (kcal mol ⁻¹)	-79241.67
3.	Energy of HOMO (eV)	-8.551373
4.	Energy of LUMO (eV)	-3.819204
5.	Binding energy (kcal mol ⁻¹)	-5195.18
6.	Isolated atomic energy (kcal mol ⁻¹)	-74046.495
7.	Electronic energy (kcal mol ⁻¹)	-664221.2
8.	Core-core interaction (kcal mol ⁻¹)	584979.5026
9.	Heat of formation (kcal mol ⁻¹)	217.6144
10.	Dipoles (Debyes)	3.52D
11.	Total charges on 'p'	+3.28344
12.	Molecular point group	C ₁
13.	Inhibition efficiency (%)	93

grinded so that a flat surface could be obtained for corrosion studies. The electrochemical cell assembly of three electrode system was used for Tafel polarization and potentiodynamic polarization studies. Corrosion studies were conducted in 1 N H₂SO₄ in presence of difference concentration 10⁻³ M, 10⁻⁵ M, 10⁻⁷ M of PTPPB. A saturated calomel electrode was used as reference electrode, platinum as counter electrode and mild steel as working

electrode. The temperature of the cell was controlled by thermostatically using JULABO-40 circulating thermostat. Infrared spectroscopy was recorded in KBr medium, using Perkin-Elmer Infrared Spectroscopie IR-37 for IR spectra. A saturated solution of the inhibitor was prepared in dry chloroform. The solution was added to a small quantity of silica gel and stirred vigorously. The solvent evaporated and the sample was dried. Small quantity of dry sample used for FTIR analysis. Surface analytical technique was performed on JEOL-840 scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Specimen were thoroughly washed in double distilled water and dried in a desiccator prior to SEM investigation.

Conclusion

From the overall data of adsorption of PTPPB on mild steel surface in acid solution was studied with the help of galvanostatic, temperature kinetics, potentiostatic polarization studies, surface characterization, scanning electron microscopy, infrared studies and quantum chemical calculation. It can be concluded that :

- (i) PTPPB retard corrosion at ordinary temperature but enhance it at higher temperature. This shows that they belong to putilovas 1st category of inhibitor.

- (ii) PTPPB are mixed inhibitor shows neither appreciable shift of E_{corr} towards any direction nor insignificant shift of OCP value (Open Current corrosion Potential).
- (iii) Irregular trends in Tafel slope values indicates that adsorption of the inhibiting species is assisted by other ions present in the solution.
- (iv) Temkin's and Freundlich's theory is adequate for explaining adsorption isotherm at all temperatures because it is multi layer adsorption.
- (v) Value of Q and E_{eff} indicate PTPPB is chemisorbed on the mild steel.
- (vi) Inhibition efficiency decrease with increase in temperature but it shows better inhibiting properties over wider range of temperature.
- (vii) From potentiodynamic studies it has been concluded that this inhibitor strongly adsorbed over metal surface and are good passivators in 1 N H_2SO_4 . This passivation depends of already adsorbed anions of the medium.
- (viii) Quantum chemical calculation shows that PTPPB is a better inhibitor because of synergistic effect of Br^- .

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